

EPDOS – WHITE PAPER – TEAM SCIENCE - AUTHOR CONTRIBUTOR DATA (CREDIT)

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Figure1 : 14 badges depicting roles from the Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT),
Source: <https://github.com/mozillascience/PaperBadger/tree/master/public/img/badge>

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SUMMARY

Scientific research in the 21st century has become teamwork combining different forms of expertise.

In this project, we investigate whether the different experts involved in the creation of a scientific result can be mapped.

We do this by analysing roles (experts) from the CRediT taxonomy extracted (retrospectively) from Elsevier publications (2020 to 2022). This covers 1.16 Million publications with CRediT expertise data. (See the specific results of the analysis report: [here](#)). CRediT data has also been made available to institutes to carry out institutional-level analyses. This represents about 14 thousand publications with CRediT expertise data for the Netherlands. Furthermore, within this project discussions were held with

Crossref to include the CRediT data in the Crossref metadata schema so that via CrossRef the CRediT data can be taken from publishers. (NB. For almost all Elsevier journals, CRediT roles have been recorded (in a structured way) during the article submission process since 2024. Elsevier recommends that its publishing partners (societies) do the same. [[link to author guidelines](#)]

With this new information, universities are able to gain more and structured/substantiated insight into the diversity and team play of different areas of expertise within their scientific research and act on this 'data-driven'.

This supports, for example, new forms of recognition and appreciation, enabling new career paths for 'supporting expertises like research data management, literature research or, for example, team players who are experts in data analysis, R, visualisation, etc.'

By collecting and offering such data in the organisation's research information system, concrete pilots become possible.

What the project achieved:

1. **CRediT-contribution-parser:** Elsevier has developed and made publicly available an algorithm that allows retrospective assignment of CRediT roles to authors in existing publications with an 'author contribution' section. [[link to code and method](#)].
2. **CRediT contributions report:** Elsevier used the data extracted from ScienceDirect (total dataset of ~1.1million records from the years 2020-2022) to produce a report showing the distribution of those CRediT roles across countries, institutions and seniority. [[link to analysis report](#)]

Figure2 : a slide from the report, showing a distribution of CRediT roles distributed across a number of disciplines in the Netherlands .

3. **CRediT contributions data for Dutch Pilot partners:** The pilot partners have each received a dataset with the CRediT roles for their own institution. [[link to data](#)]
4. **CRediT contributions in Crossref metadata:** The project aims to also get these additional CRediT roles into the public domain by attaching it in Crossref. Discussions with Crossref have

taken place, with Crossref indicating the need to adapt the metadata schema. This modification is on the roadmap for Q1&2 2025. [link to announcement on [niso](#) and [crossref](#) blogs].

5. **CRedit as a feature in PURE and other CRIS systems.** It is the ambition of this project to treat CRedit data as any other critical meta data in the various institutional information systems; at the recent PURE conference, the inclusion of CRedit in Pure was discussed as a session topic. There is also interest in this in Scotland. The conference also included a discussion with metadata specialists from Elsevier about the adaptations in Pure needed for this. This is being explored further, but seems possible with a limited number of changes.
6. **CRedit contributions in institutional data analyses and use case studies:** each of the institutions (research intelligence teams) used the data available to the institutions has been used to make analyses, and to use these analyses as examples in the use case studies. The examples show, for example, that support roles are often underexposed in publications by some departments. These analyses could be useful in team compositions in the future. For the use case studies, the examples were presented to internal users (faculty policy officers responsible for reports and diversity).

Comments from user studies were mixed, ranging from enthusiasm for progression to scepticism about implementation in certain disciplines. Part of the comments were about the analysis having too much of a focus on the research domain, and not education, valorisation and leadership which is also what the new Recognition & Appreciation is about. While this is an important insight, it is also mainly due to the scope of this project, the nature of the source data, the CRedit taxonomy and the focus of research intelligence teams.

Figure3 : Draft Dashboard from VU Research Intelligence for this EPDOS Team Science project. [[open here](#)]

INTRODUCTION

In this white paper, we explain to you what the CRedit taxonomy is, how widely it has been implemented and how it can provide insight in analyses for Team Science.

This "Teams Science Author CRedit Data" project was set up from "Elsevier Partnership Dutch Open Science"

More can be found at:

<https://epdos.nl/pilots/team-science-author-contributor-data-credit/> .

Contributors to this include Elsevier, Amsterdam UMC, Maastricht University, Rijksuniversiteit Groningen, TU Eindhoven and Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam.

REASON / BACKGROUND / WHAT WE ALREADY KNEW

The work of researchers has become increasingly diverse in recent decades. In the past, a researcher was integrally responsible for the entire research, and received full credit as the author of his or her article. Nowadays, scientific research often involves many different skills needed in a scientific team to answer the research question.

One of the main Open Science goals of Dutch research is to redefine the reward and recognition of all actors in this modern and complex academic world: valuing the different roles in Team Science. To properly recognise & reward, contributions must be captured - in a consistent manner - to ensure that everyone is recognised fairly and teams can be evaluated transparently.

The NISO standard classification scheme (CRediT) describes 14 specific roles in research projects. Publishers are implementing this classification scheme in their journals so that the specific roles of different contributors to submitted papers can be recorded. These 'author contribution' statements are often already present in JATS-XML metadata, sometimes as unstructured text and increasingly as structured metadata.

If this data becomes structured the data could be used to gain insights for the development of team science over the years.

WHAT IS CREDIT?

CRediT ([Contributor Roles Taxonomy](#)) is an initiative to recognise individual contributions to scientific research. It was introduced in 2012 following a workshop organised by Harvard University and the Wellcome Trust, with the aim of finding ways to make scientific contributions more visible and valued. It has become an NISO standard and in the following years has been increasingly widely embraced by publishers and implemented in the metadata of scientific publications.

ROLL

CRediT provides a high-over taxonomy, consisting of 14 roles, reflecting the various contributions individuals can make to a scientific output. For example, Supervision, Writing - Editing, Data Curation, Conceptualisation, etc. These roles are designed to be applicable to all areas of scientific activity. Please refer to the appendix for a description of the roles.

IMPLEMENTATION

When submitting a publication to a journal, *multiple roles* can be assigned *per contributor*, and a specific role can be assigned to multiple contributors. When multiple contributors perform the same role, the *level of their contribution* can *optionally* be specified as 'leading', 'equal' or 'supporting'. Corresponding authors bear responsibility for assigning roles, and all contributors should be given the opportunity to review and confirm assigned roles.

THE PURPOSE OF THIS PILOT IS TO ASSESS:

- 1 Whether and how contributor data is able to enable the use cases around team science and enable.
- 2 To what extent papers published in the Netherlands (initially from Elsevier proprietary journals) can sufficiently capture the CRediT roles of the various authors (high percentage of authors with a defined contributor role).
- 3 what set of (reporting) data is needed that research intelligence teams can use to provide insights/answers to the various use cases around team science and contributor data (see below).

USE CASES (WHY ARE WE DOING THIS?):

- **Individual development and recognition:** Individual level & new career paths: at the individual level, researchers can show their development as professional researchers over time and be recognised for it. This can also enable new career paths, for example for researchers primarily involved in a software application to published research. The data can also be used to support a narrative in assessment processes and in CVs.
- **Team analysis:** Department level: at the department or group level, principal investigators or department heads can plot their team members based on their most prominent role(s) and analyse the gap between desired and current team members. They could also do this on a larger scale in a strategic staff planning process or find existing experts easier to work with elsewhere.
- **Strategic publications:** At the departmental and institutional level, CRediT data could be used to determine relevant publications for strategic planning and review purposes of the institution.
- **Faculty support:** It will be possible for faculties to form a strategic policy for local support. If certain roles are over-represented or if certain tasks that could be centrally organised are lacking in faculty, this insight could be used to make a business case for setting up support tasks at faculty level rather than by research group.
- **Collaboration:** collaborations: researchers or project leaders can analyse the division of roles across the niche of their research topic. And seek new collaborations if a team lacks a certain role. This is possible within an institute, but also outside, to encourage new collaborations.

METHOD FOLLOWED / WHAT DID WE DO

To obtain sufficient structured data for the use case analyses now and in the future, as part of the strategic cooperation with Elsevier, two routes were taken. One, prospectively, via an adaptation of journal submission platforms. And two, retrospectively, via text-mining of ScienceDirect data.

Retrospectively obtaining structured CRediT data: Elsevier owns a database, Science Direct, with publications as full-text XML files. A good number of those XML files contain an "Author contribution" section, containing a statement about the contribution made by authors. In , this already uses the CRediT taxonomy, too small for faculty-level analyses. And in part this is free wording, still unusable for analysis. For the latter part, Elsevier used a text-mining algorithm and trained AI components to upgrade the unstructured text from the author contribution section to structured text. They did this by linking the author for each publication (via accurate matching via Scopus data) and the CRediT role (via a specifically trained AI classifier for CRediT roles).

Functioning of text-mining algorithm: Elsevier used text-mining to extract the authors' roles from the research papers and matched them to the CRediT taxonomy. The research papers are from ScienceDirect database, as the JATS-XML of the paper is available there. In the XML, we looked at the "Author contribution" section. Two matches were made there. Match 1: the author's name with the Scopus Author ID, based on the corresponding EID from Scopus and Science direct. Match 2: the description of the role in the XML section based on a retrained SciBERT model. The training data (gpt4_labeled.csv) contained 10,000 lines of text with variations of a role description along with the CRediT role label. These 10,000 entries were generated with GTP4 based on a manually annotated sample (gpt_annotation.csv) of 1,000 lines and the descriptions from the CRediT taxonomy. For more explanation and the exact operation, follow the link to the [code and method](#).

Text-mining In figures (period 2012 to 2022)*

- A. 5.5M publications in Science Direct dataset for period 2012-2022
- B. 1.2M publications with "contributor statements" were found in the Science Direct data set (# 1,219,214)
- C. 660K (54% of B) of these already had structured CRedit role information (in the contributor role xml tags) (#659,521)
- D. 560K (46% of B) had no structured data; but role information included as "raw text". (#559.693)
- E. 501K (90% of D) of these unstructured "raw text" statements could be matched with the 14 CRediT roles via the text-mining pipeline (about 90%). (#501.295)
- F. 1.16M (21% of A) publications in total, are after the text-mining pipeline, with CRediT role information available for analysis. (#1.160.816)
- G. 40k Dutch publications in Science Direct dataset for period 2020-2022
- H. 14k (35% of G) Dutch publications with structured CRedIT statements, after text-mining
- I. Number of publications with CRediT statements per participating institution :
 - o RUG: #1528 | VU: #1225 | Amsterdam UMC: #1139| UM: #1043| TUE: 801

* note that from 2012 to 2020 the # number of papers with author contribution information was very low. Since 2020, we see a very rapid increase. The analyses done by Elsevier therefore focused on 2020-2022 dataset.

CRediT statements in Science Direct data

The number of Science Direct publications with CRediT statements has been gradually increasing since the development of the taxonomy in 2012.

From 2020, the share of publications with CRediT statements experienced a significant increase up to 47% in 2022.

The figures likely indicate wider adoption among the publishers, journals and academics in the recent years.

Analytical Services

Figure4: CRediT taxonomy will be applied to a few single publications from 2012, but will rapidly take off from 2020 onwards.

Limited period: The retrospective action (analyses) was limited to publications from Science Direct for the years 2020, 2021 and 2022, also because relatively little information on author roles was added in earlier years (in less than 1% - 4% of publications).

Algorithm Transparency: In the creation of the text-mining algorithm, many choices and decisions were made to make it work well. This may raise questions about, for example, why an author is not matched, or why a classification group is underrepresented. Therefore, Elsevier has decided to make the source code and documentation of the text-mining algorithm publicly available via Github.

<https://github.com/elsevierlabs-os/credit-contribution-parser>

Data Scope & General Insights: Elsevier analysed the data to arrive at a basic understanding of this data. In doing so, they looked at the distribution of the 14 roles by subject area (according to ASJC categories), seniority (authors with more vs less than 10 years of publication history), by country (selection of 7 EU countries, including the Netherlands), and a distribution of roles within subject areas in the Netherlands. For the [full report, follow this link](#).

Figure5 : The availability of CRediT Statements in science direct varies slightly by country.

Use case studies & insights from the institutions: The data with CRediT roles was shared with the participating institutions in different files. They in turn have processed the data to come up with better insights with the internal users for answering the use cases.

Looking ahead obtaining structured CRediT data via adaptation to journal submission platforms: Linking author roles from plain text to the CRediT taxonomy is not a desirable situation. Therefore, Elsevier has implemented the CRediT taxonomy in their journals and submission systems. Journals published by Elsevier on behalf of societies will also increasingly support the CRediT taxonomy. The use of CRediT statements are defined in [the Elsevier guidelines for authors](#).

Making structured CRediT data publicly available via Crossref: These structured CRediT statements would initially be made available only to pilot participants. To make this data publicly available, the most common route is to do so via CrossRef. Crossref is a not-for-profit organisation that issues DOIs and stores and redistributes the associated metadata under a [CC0 public domain licence](#). In contact with Crossref, it appears that this is not technically possible at the moment, as their metadata schema does not yet have a place for Author contribution descriptions. This adaptation is on the roadmap for Q1&2 2025. Read the announcement on the [niso](#) and [crossref](#) blogs.

OUTCOMES OF USE CASES

Some of the pilot participants combined the CRediT data with information from their CRIS system and used it to create overviews or reports. With these overviews or reports, in some cases information was retrieved from faculty managers and policymakers around the use cases. Below, we briefly describe the

use case again, what we intended to do, what the response was from the user groups, and what the recommendations are.

To illustrate each use case, we have included an illustration of VU's draft team science dashboards. [\[open interactive dashboard here\]](#) Each participating institution created its own representation of the data. These can all be found as datasets attached to this report. See: [10.5281/zenodo.14446400](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14446400)

USE CASE 1: INDIVIDUAL DEVELOPMENT - CAREER PATHS

Description:

This use case focuses on using CRediT taxonomy to show individual researchers their professional growth over time, including new career paths. It provides support for CV preparation, assessment processes and narratives.

What we aimed to do:

We wanted to explore how CRediT data can be used to make individual contributions more visible and support the Recognise & Appreciate programme.

Figure6 : Dashboard Usecase1; shows changes of roles (CRediT statements) over time. (Period too limited for a career path, but offers potential)

Response from user groups:

There was broad interest in this use case, particularly as it ties in directly with the Recognition & Rewards programmes. Users found it potentially valuable to support new career paths, such as for researchers specialising in software development or data management.

Recommendations:

- Integrate CRediT taxonomy into existing assessment and career processes.
- Develop tools that allow researchers to visually present their contributions, such as dashboards or CV templates.

- Start pilot projects in disciplines that already have strong team science cultures, such as natural sciences.

USE CASE 2: TEAM ANALYSIS - DEPARTMENT LEVEL

Description:

CRedit data can be used at the departmental level to analyse team members according to their roles and identify any gaps in expertise or capacity. This supports strategic workforce planning and team building.

What we aimed to do:

We wanted to explore how departments or research groups can use CRedit data to optimise teams and support strategic decisions.

Figure 7 : Dashboard Usecase 2; shows a radar plot of a department, with total number of contributions per CRedit statement. Below on the left is a table showing teammates and total numbers of contributions in which capacity. This dashboard shows which roles are over and underrepresented in a team.

Response from user groups:

Users were positive about the potential for team analysis, but stressed that the relevance depends heavily on the research field. Fields such as natural and life sciences saw more potential than humanities, for example.

Recommendations:

- Focus on research fields where team science already plays a prominent role.
- Develop tools that enable team roles to be understood and support strategic decisions.
- Organise faculty workshops to explore the application of team analysis.

USE CASE 3: STRATEGIC PLANNING

Description:

This use case explores the use of CRediT taxonomy to identify and use strategic publications for institutional review and planning.

What we aimed to do:

We wanted to see if CRediT data could support institutions in identifying priority publications for strategic purposes.

Figure 8 : Dashboard Usecase 3; shows a table of a department's publications, sorted by number of contributions by teammates. This shows the publications to which the team has contributed significantly, and in what capacity.

Reaction from user groups:

This use case resonated less well with users. The value for strategic publications was not widely recognised, and there was more interest in applications at the individual or team level.

Recommendations:

- De-prioritise this use case and focus on applications with more impact, such as career development and team analysis.
- Explore alternative ways of using publication data, e.g. for networking or collaboration.

USE CASE 4: FACULTY SUPPORT

Description:

CRediT data can support faculties in developing strategic policies by providing insight into over-represented roles and missing expertise. This can be used to make a business case for shared support roles at faculty level.

What we aimed to do:

We wanted to gain insight into how faculties can use CRediT to make strategic choices, for example in developing support for roles that are consistently lacking or overloaded.

Figure9 : Dashboard Use Case 4; Shows a radar plot for a faculty with number of contributions per CRedit Statement. This shows which roles within a faculty are over- and under-represented in publications.

Response from user groups:

Users found this an interesting application, especially for faculties facing limited resources and considering centralisation of support. There was a need for concrete examples and case studies to further explore this application.

Recommendations:

- Use CRediT analyses to identify under- or over-represented roles within faculties.
- Develop pilot projects in which faculties prepare business cases for centralised support tasks.
- Work with HR teams to integrate these insights into strategic workforce planning.

USE CASE 5: COLLABORATION - WITHIN AND OUTSIDE INSTITUTIONS

Description:

CRediT data can be used to strengthen partnerships by analysing roles within teams and finding potential partners with complementary expertise.

What we aimed to do:

We wanted to gain insight into how researchers and project leaders can use CRediT to fill gaps in their teams and seek collaborative partnerships.

Figure10 : Use Case 5: Display from a faculty a table of researchers who have contributed to the 'software' CRediT statement in publications. This allows expertise within a faculty to be found within other departments.

Response from user groups:

Users saw potential in this application, especially for seeking expertise within and outside the institution. There was also interest in using this data for strategic networking.

Recommendations:

- Develop a searchable database based on CRediT metadata to identify experts.
- Encourage diversity in team compositions by using role analysis.
- Test these applications in a pilot programme with multiple institutions.

OUTCOMES FOR PROJECT GOALS

Goal 1: Whether and how contributor data enables use cases around team science

The project made a significant contribution to exploring and applying contributor data to support use cases around team science. The development of the CRediT-contribution-parser algorithm allowed retrospective assignment of roles to authors, which was an essential step in providing insight into the various contributions within research projects. This insight has been applied in use cases such as career development, team analysis and collaboration, with positive feedback from user groups, especially within science fields where team science is more prominent.

Yet there were also challenges. Comments from users showed that the applicability of the data varied widely across disciplines and that broader uses, such as teaching and valorisation, were beyond the scope of the project. This suggests that further expansion of the dataset and additional metadata are needed to support a wider range of use cases.

Target 2: The extent to which Dutch publications capture CRediT roles

The project has shown that a significant amount of publications now feature structured CRediT roles, thanks in part to retrospective text-mining methods. For the years 2020-2022, 35% of Dutch publications in ScienceDirect now contain CRediT data, providing a solid basis for further analysis. In addition, Elsevier has started integrating CRediT roles into their submission platforms, providing a sustainable solution for new publications.

However, there remains a challenge in the adoption of CRediT roles among other publishers and disciplines, as well as in increasing coverage within the Netherlands. The proportion of publications with missing or incomplete contribution information remains a concern, especially for disciplines where multidisciplinary work is less well documented.

Goal 3: The required set of data for research intelligence teams

The project has provided valuable insights into the data and analysis methods needed by research intelligence teams. The datasets made available have enabled institutions to conduct team science analyses and develop concrete applications, such as dashboards and reports. These tools have helped identify gaps in team roles and support strategic workforce planning.

However, user feedback also showed that the usability of this data could be further enhanced by additional metadata and broader integration with systems such as CRIS and HR tools. Moreover, there was a clear need for more focus on data consistency and accessibility, especially for disciplines where team science is less prominent.

CONCLUSION AND FOLLOW-UP STEPS

The project has made important steps towards achieving the project goals and provides a solid foundation for further development. At the same time, clear follow-up steps are needed to increase the impact and make the results more widely applicable.

FOLLOW-UP STEPS

1. **Accessibility:** Making metadata on author roles publicly available is essential. Currently, this data is often restricted to proprietary databases, which goes against the principles of open science and responsible research evaluation as set out in the Leiden Manifesto and COARA. To ensure this accessibility, strong collaboration with parties such as Crossref is crucial.
2. **Data portability:** Crossref should include author roles in their data model and integrate metadata from Elsevier and other publishers. This integration is expected to be ready for production by media 2025, which is an important step in making the data available to a wider audience.
3. **System integration:** For effective application, authoring roles must be able to be seamlessly captured in systems such as CRIS, PURE, (data) repositories and publishing systems. This requires technical support and uniform implementation of standards.
4. **Expanding the dataset:** The text mining algorithm used in this project should be applied to Dutch publications from recent years to obtain a more complete picture of career paths and the situation in the Netherlands. This should take into account the limitation that the algorithm can currently only match authors in the Scopus database.
5. **Policy development:** Universities involved in initiatives such as Recognise & Appreciate should be actively involved in conversations about the application of author roles in creating diverse

career paths. This requires further collaboration between institutions, policymakers and research communities.

6. **System support:** HR and CRIS systems need to be prepared to support the diversification of roles and career paths. This requires technological adaptations and new processes for data management and career development.

CONCLUSION

To further strengthen the impact of this project, structural investments in accessibility, data portability, and systems integration are necessary. In addition, policy engagement and expansion of the dataset are essential to make the results widely applicable and align with national and international efforts on open science and responsible research evaluation. These follow-up steps form the basis for embedding the insights from this project in academic practice and creating a sustainable system of recognition and appreciation.

REFERENCE LIST

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ANNEXES

CREDIT'S 14 CONTRIBUTOR ROLES

CRediT - Contributor Role Taxonomy: <https://credit.niso.org/>

Dutch translation of CRediT:

<https://contributorshipcollaboration.github.io/projects/translation/translations/nl/>

Dutch	English
Conceptualisatie	Conceptualization
Ideeën; formulering of evolutie van overkoepelende onderzoeksdoelen en -doelstellingen.	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims.
Datacuratie	Data Curation
Beheersactiviteiten voor het annoteren (metadata produceren), het opschonen en het onderhouden van onderzoeksgegevens (inclusief softwarecode, waar dit nodig is voor het interpreteren van de gegevens zelf) voor initieel gebruik en later hergebruik.	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later re-use.
Formele analyse	Formal Analysis
Toepassing van statistische, wiskundige, computationele of andere formele technieken om studiegegevens te analyseren of te synthetiseren.	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyse or synthesize study data.
Fondsenwerving	Funding Acquisition
Verwerving van de financiële steun voor het project dat heeft geleid tot deze publicatie.	Acquisition of the financial support for the project leading to this publication.
Onderzoek	Investigation
Uitvoeren van een onderzoeksproces, in het bijzonder het uitvoeren van de experimenten of het verzamelen van gegevens/bewijsmateriaal.	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection.
Methodologie	Methodology
De ontwikkeling of het ontwerp van de methodologie; het maken van modellen.	Development or design of methodology; creation of models.
Projectadministratie	Project Administration

Dutch	English
Verantwoordelijk voor het beheer en de coördinatie van de planning en de uitvoering van onderzoeksactiviteiten.	Management and coordination responsibility for the research activity planning and execution.
Middelen	Resources
Voorziening van studiematerialen, reagentia, materialen, patiënten, laboratoriummonsters, dieren, instrumentatie, computerbronnen of andere analyse-instrumenten.	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools.
Software	Software
Programmeren, softwareontwikkeling; ontwerpen van computerprogramma's; implementatie van de computercode en ondersteunende algoritmen; testen van bestaande codecomponenten.	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components.
Supervisie	Supervision
Verantwoordelijk voor het toezicht en het leiden van de planning en de uitvoering van onderzoeksactiviteiten, inclusief mentorschap buiten het kernteam.	Oversight and leadership responsibility for the research activity planning and execution, including mentorship external to the core team.
Validatie	Validation
Verificatie, al dan niet als onderdeel van de activiteit, van de algemene replicatie/herhaalbaarheid van resultaten/experimenten en andere onderzoeksresultaten.	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs.
Visualisatie	Visualization
Vorbereiding, creatie en/of presentatie van het gepubliceerde werk, in het bijzonder visualisatie/data presentatie.	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically visualization/data presentation.
Schrijven – eerste versie	Writing – Original Draft Preparation
Vorbereiding, creatie en/of presentatie van het gepubliceerde werk, in het bijzonder het schrijven van de initiële versie (inclusief inhoudelijke vertaling).	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work, specifically writing the initial draft (including substantive translation).
Schrijven – review en bewerking	Writing – Review & Editing

Dutch	English
Vorbereiding, creatie en/of presentatie van het gepubliceerde werk door de leden van de oorspronkelijke onderzoeksgroep, in het bijzonder kritische beoordeling, commentaar of revisie – inclusief pre- of post-publicatiefasen.	Preparation, creation and/or presentation of the published work by those from the original research group, specifically critical review, commentary or revision – including pre- or post-publication stages.

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